

1 **Kinase targeting in basal-like breast cancer: STK17B.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Breast cancer can be distinguished into two broad groups, luminal and basal, based on cytologic,
7 morphologic, cytoskeletal and differentiation-based features. While luminal breast cancers can be positive
8 for expression of a hormone receptor (ESR/PGR/AR) or a growth factor receptor (ERBB2) and targeted
9 accordingly clinically, basal-like breast cancers cannot. Inadequate long-term control of disease (e.g.,
10 partial response [PR] or recurrence/relapse) reflects limited effectiveness of existing drugs that treat basal
11 subtype disease. Here we utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to define the basal-like breast
12 cancer kinome and phosphatome by measuring total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with
13 basal-like as compared to luminal A and luminal B breast cancer to identify basal-like signaling features.
14 We describe one member of a group of kinases up-regulated and differentially expressed in human
15 basal-like breast cancer, STK17B, as a catalytically available enzyme and candidate therapeutic target for
16 the adjunctive medical treatment of basal subtype breast cancer.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human basal subtype and triple negative organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with basal subtype breast cancers or TNBC with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in basal subtype disease with rapidity and ease.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through study of the basal-like tumor transcriptome: a kinase target that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: STK17B.

Results

Figure 1: STK17B is differentially expressed in basal subtype breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal subtype

n=59 luminal A and luminal B breast cancer
n=43 basal subtype breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205214_at	6.82E-05	-4.155426	0.78826	-0.98816942	STK17B	9531/29873	68.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the tumors of humans with luminal A breast cancer or luminal B breast cancer as compared to that of basal subtype breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of serine/threonine kinase 17B, encoded by *STK17B* in basal subtype breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of STK17B changed more than nearly 70% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of STK17B messenger RNA in basal subtype tumors, suggesting up-regulation of STK17B during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the basal breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal subtype

n=77 luminal A and luminal B breast cancer
n=14 basal-like breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8057887	1.33e-01	-1.5154024	-5.64813	-0.2487752	STK17B	13387/33297	59.8

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with luminal A and luminal B breast cancers relative to basal subtype breast cancers in a second microarray dataset (6)

1 from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of
2 STK17B in basal subtype breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of STK17B here changed
3 more than nearly 60% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose
4 expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change
5 indicating increased quantity of STK17B messenger RNA in basal subtype tumors, suggesting
6 up-regulation of STK17B during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the basal breast
7 cancer subtype.

8 Thus, differential and increased expression of STK17B defines the transcriptional landscape of the
9 basal or basal-like breast cancer subtype in humans.

10 **Discussion**

11 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
12 treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
13 tamoxifen and letrozole). We recently used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple
14 phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and
15 fortuitously found their decreased expression was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients
16 with another subtype of breast cancer, HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A multi-kinase approach delivered
17 in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and
18 activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Murthy, R.K., Loi, S., Okines, A., Paplomata, E., Hamilton, E., Hurvitz, S.A., Lin, N.U., Borges, V., Abramson, V., Anders, C. and Bedard, P.L., 2020. Tucatinib, trastuzumab, and capecitabine for HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(7), pp.597-609.
2. Stavrou, E., Winer, E.P. and Lin, N.U., 2021. How we treat HER2-positive brain metastases. *ESMO open*, 6(5), p.100256.
3. Kay, C., Martínez-Pérez, C., Meehan, J., Gray, M., Webber, V., Dixon, J.M. and Turnbull, A.K., 2021. Current trends in the treatment of HR+/HER2+ breast cancer. *Future Oncology*, 17(13), pp.1665-1681.
4. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
5. GSE45827: Gruosso, T., Mieulet, V., Cardon, M., Bourachot, B., Kieffer, Y., Devun, F., Dubois, T., Dutreix, M., Vincent-Salomon, A., Miller, K.M. and Mehta-Grigoriou, F., 2016. Chronic oxidative stress promotes H2AX protein degradation and enhances chemosensitivity in breast cancer patients. *EMBO molecular medicine*, 8(5), pp.527-549.
6. GSE87049: Romero-Cordoba, S.L., Salido-Guadarrama, I., Rebollar-Vega, R., Bautista-Piña, V., Dominguez-Reyes, C., Tenorio-Torres, A., Villegas-Carlos, F., Fernández López, J.C., Uribe-Figueroa, L., Alfaro-Ruiz, L. and Hidalgo-Miranda, A., 2021. Comprehensive omic characterization of breast cancer in Mexican-Hispanic women. *Nature communications*, 12(1), pp.1-1.
7. Koike-Yusa, H., Li, Y., Tan, E.P., Velasco-Herrera, M.D.C. and Yusa, K., 2014. Genome-wide recessive genetic screening in mammalian cells with a lentiviral CRISPR-guide RNA library. *Nature biotechnology*, 32(3), pp.267-273.
8. Shah, A.N., Davey, C.F., Whitebirch, A.C., Miller, A.C. and Moens, C.B., 2015. Rapid reverse genetic screening using CRISPR in zebrafish. *Nature methods*, 12(6), pp.535-540.
9. Pan, A., Liu, L., Wang, C., Guo, H., Hao, X., Wang, Q., Huang, J., He, N., Yu, H., Lin, X. and Wei, S., 2020. Association of public health interventions with the epidemiology of the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China. *Jama*, 323(19), pp.1915-1923.
10. Lin, N.U. and Winer, E.P., 2007. Brain metastases: the HER2 paradigm. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 13(6), pp.1648-1655.
11. Ponzoni, O., Antonelli, G., Martinelli, G., Baglio, F., Zaniboni, S., Canino, F., Barbolini, M., Molinaro, A., Moschetti, L., Piacentini, F. and Dominici, M., 2024. 208P Clinicopathological factors and treatment management in HER2+ breast cancer patients with central nervous system metastasis. *ESMO Open*.
12. Nader-Marta, G., Martins-Branco, D. and De Azambuja, E., 2022. How we treat patients with metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer. *ESMO open*, 7(1), p.100343.
13. Leyland-Jones, B., 2009. Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive breast cancer and central nervous system metastases. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 27(31), pp.5278-5286.
14. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PPP4C is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
15. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PLPP2 is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
16. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE45827 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in basal subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, as compared to luminal A or luminal B breast cancers (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).